

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NYAMITWE****FIRST NAME: ALAIN AIME****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

The author used the following software: (MS Word - Office 365 on Windows 11)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text:

1. Essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 7-12)
2. Rules of thumb for writing academic papers (12-14)
3. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
5. Latin abbreviations and expressions (EUCLID 2021, 58-64)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The course ACA-401D has given me deep insight into English academic writing and its difference from other types of writing. For the most of my education and work, I have written in French. For a certain time, I wrote for newspapers, which is another totally different style. The diplomatic arena uses a number of Latin expressions, which have become almost automatic because of long practice. This course has given me more information on the context of those terms and expressions.

Therefore, I take this course very seriously as it introduces me to appropriate academic writing.

In the context of this paper, I will discuss the concepts of essay writing, the rules of thumb for writing a paper, the difference between American and British English, and why plagiarism is not an acceptable option in academic writing. Furthermore, I will discuss the use of Latin abbreviations and expressions.

2) ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

All kinds of writing follow some logic. Academic writing is no exception. The course indicates that from analyzing the question and defining the key terms to handing in the essay, the academic writer has to establish the points of view, research the topic by using credible academic sources, take notes from his/her preliminary reading, develop the essay and organize ideas, draft the essay into main parts and give it a proper proofreading process (EUCLID 2021, 8).

There can be no academic writing without research because one needs to gather knowledge about a topic before sharing it with the public. The course ACA-401 shows the way by breaking down a four-pronged sequence: assessment of what you already know about the topic, what you need to read and know, verification if the material is useful to the topic, and determine if the material can be used to support one's answer. Of course, notes need to be made at every step of the reading route (EUCLID 2021, 8).

This process is quite logical because if one has to go about the work seriously, one has to get the ideas right, and this can only happen if these are identified and structured. Ideas, concepts, and explanations emanate from real people or organizations, which is the reason why they need to be properly identified and attributed. We shall see why this is very important when we analyze plagiarism's dangers (v. infra). ACA-401D suggests the establishment of a plan that will i. a “decide on a possible answer to the question, select the information..., decide which points you will discuss and in which order” (EUCLID 2021, 8-9).

The course suggests a format in three stages while respecting logic: an introduction where we move from the general to the specific, answer the question with a thesis statement, provide a road map; the body where the answer to the main question, knowledge of the materials, examples, quotes,... are provided, and the conclusion where the answer is restated, where once again the summary of the main points are given, and where possible implications or future directions for research are indicated without however introducing new information or ideas (EUCLID 2021, 10). I find that this process allows a full and comprehensive grasp of the matter and leaves nothing to chance. The reader will thus fully understand the issues raised in the paper.

It is important to note that each paragraph should develop one idea when writing an essay. Sentences and examples that are part of it should all explain, support, or relate to the said idea.

It is advised to start writing earlier and start with the body, the introduction, and the conclusion being written later on.

3) RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING A PAPER

For the paper to be complete, it is important to state at the outset of the paper the reason why you are writing. The writer needs to be focused and stick to the idea announced at the beginning of the paper. The course suggests that the ideas have to be clearly expressed in a way that each reader will be able to understand the idea (s) you are developing. This entails some elegance in writing to keep the reader's attention and avoid quoting anyhow, and choosing only those relevant to the idea or thesis being developed.

Another rule of thumb that the course prescribes is the avoidance of plagiarism as this means using some author's ideas, words, and sentences without recognizing them. It is utter theft in the academic circle. I will come back to it later.

4) AMERICAN VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

French has an Academy that keeps reviewing the language. Regularly, that highly reputed body announces new words, which are incorporated into the dictionaries. The French Academy has jurisdiction over all the variants of French, whether it is Quebecois or France's, or the islands' French, and clears the Grammar textbooks. That doesn't seem to be the case with the English language.

The American English seems to be very imaginative as many new words are created and introduced in the public parlance. The course finds that the importance of the USA in World affairs and the economy explains why American English is influential. However, Academic English is almost uniform, although some exceptions exist.

Some words are written the same way but pronounced differently. Some examples include words like schedules, renaissance, secretary, etcetera (EUCLID 2021, 25). Other words are spelled differently, even if their pronunciation is different. For instance, the words defense/defence, cheque/check, manoeuvre/maneuver, tyre/tire, etcetera. The date is also differently formatted depending on whether you are writing from an American or a British perspective. You will follow the day, month, year format or month, day, year format.

Apart from the examples shared in the course pack, I personally know of petrol/gas station and other words which do not exist in British English. For example, in the American English, "the car was totaled" means that the car was completely destroyed. The Texas insurance informs that "The insurance company will look at the value of your car vs. the cost to repair it. If the cost to repair the car is about the same or more than the value of your car, the insurance company will likely consider it totaled" (TDI, n.d.).

In the American Diplomatic parlance, one term which is particularly interesting, is the verb to "png." Quite often we hear of diplomats who were declared "persona non grata" (cf. inf). An American diplomat will simply tell you that "Iran has "pnged" our First Secretary."

This means that the writer needs to choose which type of English he will use and be consistent in all its aspects: words, punctuation, date format, quotation, etcetera. Indeed, it would be misleading if some parts of the text were written in British English, with typical British words, while others would be full of American English words or expressions.

5) PLAGIARISM

As indicated earlier, plagiarism is to be avoided by all means. It is what I would call the original sin in Academic writing. Plagiarism exists when citing a portion of a text drawn from some resources without giving credit to the author. I find that one of the subtlest ways of plagiarizing is paraphrasing other authors and not recognizing them.

Plagiarism is a legal offense. It carries a penalty. In fact, it is generally against the concept of copyright which, put simply, is the right that the Law recognizes to the author of an intellectual product. Authors of books, poetry, theses, etcetera are entitled to the legal protection of their works. “Plagiarism can also result in legal action being taken against the plagiarist resulting in fines as high as \$50,000 and a jail sentence of up to one year. More serious offenses in which the plagiarist earns money of more than \$2,500 can result in a felony conviction with fines up to \$250,000 and a jail term up to 10 years” (Courtney 2021).

To avoid falling into the trap of plagiarism, it is very important to “properly cite the author or source that has provided the information you are using” (EUCLID 2021, 34). This can be done either by in-text citation or by quotations. And when paraphrasing, the words used must be an accurate representation of the author’s words and meaning.

Academia has, for many years, found ways to deter plagiarism and it is very good. However, I wonder if artificial intelligence is not a serious threat to the quality of academic work. ChatGPT is new but growing in importance and popularity. It provides “intelligent” replies to questions that humans input into the system. This means that there will be a need to protect the copyright but also the integrity of the students of today and tomorrow.

6) USE OF LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

I am particularly interested in the use of those words in a language that is sometimes referred to as “dead.” Academia, law, and diplomacy use those expressions quite often. It is recommended to use plain English, which is “a writing style that is simple and direct but not simplistic or patronizing” (EUCLID 2021, 59).

I find that some abbreviations are very frequent in the writing of academic papers: e.g., (*exempli gratia*), meaning for example, *op.cit.* (*opere citato*) which refers to sources before the immediately prior citation; Q.E.D¹ (*quod erat demonstrandum*), literally “that

¹ It has a French equivalent C.Q.F.D (*ce qu’il fallait démontrer*), often used in Mathematics.

which was to be demonstrated;” v.inf. (vide infra) and v. sup. (vide supra) respectively, meaning “see below” and “see above.”

Some expressions have earned a life of their own in areas like diplomacy and Law (v. sup.) Bona fide (good faith), de facto (from the fact), de jure (from the law), ex officio (out of one’s office), ad interim, or simply a.i. (acting), non sequitur (it does not follow), sine die (without a fixed day or time), and sine qua non (essential precondition). The last expression is often used in negotiations, while “ad interim” is used in the administration when an officer temporarily takes over the responsibilities of his/her absent manager.

It is important to note that, once again, depending on the type of English one uses, the pronunciation can be different. Stare decisis (to stand by the things decided) will be pronounced in one way by a British English practitioner and in another by an American English speaker.

7) CONCLUSION

Writing an academic essay obeys some rules, and the writer must know them. The text must be clear and flow easily. The choice of correct words and expressions, quotes attributions, the type of English to be used, and keeping in mind that “academic honesty” (i.e., “not plagiarizing) is a golden rule, are preconditions for a successful academic paper. Finally, Latin is not totally dead. Many abbreviations and expressions are still often used nowadays.

REFERENCES

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